

As on 01-04-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended to make a record of DB Taxon ID from other databases into the knowledge base system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The mainly referred other databases are; NCBI Taxonomy (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>), The Plant List (<http://www.theplantlist.org/>) and Integrated Taxonomy Information System (<https://www.itis.gov/>).
2. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.

Steps for data entry:

1. There are six fields to be entered, four of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in the 'Crop' field. Since the common name is used, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in the 'Crop Records' table.

1.2 Database (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the name of other databases that stored plant taxonomy records.
- In the database, this field is drop-down menu selection which is linked to 'Opt Taxonomy DB' table. One **MUST** first creates the database name record on the 'Opt Taxonomy DB' table.

1.3 DB Taxon ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the unique identification of taxonomy records on the other database. E.g. Taxon ID of *Pouteria campechiana* in NCBI taxonomy is 233737. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Taxonomy/Browser/wwwtax.cgi?lvl=0&id=233737>

[7](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Taxonomy/Browser/wwwtax.cgi?lvl=0&id=233737)

Pouteria campechiana

Taxonomy ID: **233737** (for references in articles please use NCBI:txid233737)

current name
Pouteria campechiana (Kunth) Baehni

NCBI BLAST name: **eudicots**

Rank: **species**

Genetic code: [Translation table 1 \(Standard\)](#)

Mitochondrial genetic code: [Translation table 1 \(Standard\)](#)

Plastid genetic code: [Translation table 11 \(Bacterial, Archaeal and Plant Plastid\)](#)

Other names:

common name(s)
canistel, eggfruit-tree, yellow sapote

1.4 URL

- This is referring to the link of the record from the other database

1.5 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the crop itself

1.6 Metadata ID (compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID